

STUDIES ON ROTATORY POWER AND CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION. PART IV.

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This paper describes the condensation products of camphor and *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde and dialkylamino-anilines with (i) camphoric anhydride and (ii) oxymethylene camphor and their rotations. The effect of dimethylamino group in *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidenecamphor is very marked; but the dialkylamino groups in dialkylaminomethylenecamphors have no specific effect. Most of these compounds were examined polarimetrically in the presence of hydrochloric acid and well marked changes in the rotatory power occurred.

The work reported in previous communications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 219, 768; 1936, **13**, 743) has been extended further and three types of compounds have been prepared. Condensation products of (a) camphor and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, (b) of camphoric anhydride with dialkylaminoanilines, and (c) of oxymethylenecamphor with the above amines.

Hilditch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 333) has prepared benzylidenecamphor with $[\alpha]_D = 425^\circ$. *p*-Dimethylaminobenzylidenecamphor (I), prepared by treating sodio-camphor with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, has $[\alpha]_D = 731^\circ$ (ethyl alcohol). The effect of dimethylamino group is, therefore, very marked. It may be of interest to compare the rotatory power of this compound with those of *p*-dimethylaminophenyliminocamphor (II) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene- β -oxynaphthylbenzylamine (III).

The replacement of CH in (I) by the nitrogen atom raised $[\alpha]_D$ from 731° to 2487° . This shows that the auxorotatory effect of the C-C and C-N linkings is not the same.

The rotatory powers of the compounds without the dimethylamino group are shown in parenthesis and it would be seen that in (III) the introduction of this group has raised the rotation twelve times. In (II) and (III) the optical influence is enhanced by the presence of the two groups of the same polarity in the *para*-position.

It is known that well-marked changes in the rotatory power occur when a substituent assumes electric charge by ionisation. Thus, $[\alpha]_D$ of *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidenecamphor in the presence of a few drops of hydrochloric acid fell from 731° to 342.8° and in methyl alcohol with seven drops of methyl iodide it fell from 704° to 621° . It is supposed that the ionisation of the quaternary salt formed is responsible for the fall in rotatory power.

The rotatory power of the *o*-diethylaminocamphoranilic acid is very small and rises considerably on the addition of hydrochloric acid. The values of this acid and those of *o*-dimethyl derivative (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 744) with and without the addition of hydrochloric acid are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

	MeOH.	EtOH.	Me ₂ CO.
<i>o</i> -Dimethyl	0	0	-9.97°
1 mol. HCl	55.00	51.13	..
<i>o</i> -Diethyl	5.00	2.00	-12.30
1 mol. HCl	38.90	20.00	7.60

The rotatory powers of the *p*-dialkylamino groups together with those of camphoranilic acids are given below.

TABLE II.

	H.	N(Me) ₂ .	N(Me)(Et).	N(Et) ₂ .	N(C ₃ H ₇) ₂ .	N(C ₄ H ₉) ₂ .
MeOH	57	69.8	60.65	83.76	44.50	55.40
	—	—	(62.54)	(91.74)	—	(64.4)
EtOH	49.8	62.4	54.60	78.16	52.90	72.70
	—	—	(58.1)	(86.20)	—	—
Me ₂ CO	38.4	54.4	47.78	85.70	43.90	60.00
MeEtCO	—	—	50.05	89.02	—	—

There is no definite order in which the dialkylamino groups could be arranged with regard to optical rotation. The diethyl compound has the largest value and the dipropyl compound the least. The compounds in some cases were examined polarimetrically in the presence of hydrochloric acid and in every case a slight increase is recorded. These values are given in brackets.

Oxymethylenecamphor readily condenses with primary and secondary amines. The rotations of the condensation products of oxymethylene-camphor with dialkylaminoanilines in various solvents are summarised below.

TABLE III.

Solvent.	N(Me) ₂ .	N(Me)(Et).	N(Et) ₂ .	N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ .	N(Me) ₂ <i>meta</i>
MeOH	339·67	333·05	303·82	326·30	322·14
	(244·56)	(240·30)	(221·35)	(291·16)	—
EtOH	305·00	330·00	315·93	336·17	340·38
Me ₂ CO	340·00	330·00	375·00	315·00	342·57
MeEtCO	359·90	338·63	366·06	331·99	302·39

These values do not differ very much from the rotatory powers of anilinomethylenecamphor which has $[\alpha]_D = 355·2^\circ$ in ethyl alcohol and $354·3^\circ$ in acetone (Singh, Bahaduri and Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 345). The dialkylamino groups in the *p*-position have got no specific effect. The only explanation which can be offered is that the phenyl group is not in close proximity to the asymmetric centre and the dialkylamino groups in the *p*-position are at a considerable distance to exert any influence.

The methyl alcohol solution of the *para* compounds was also examined with 5 drops of (N/2·05) hydrochloric acid and in each case there was a fall in the rotatory power as was expected. The values after the addition of hydrochloric acid are shown in brackets.

The methylenecamphor compounds, when dissolved in benzene and chloroform, become dark coloured and, therefore, could not be examined in these solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Dimethylaminobenzylidenecamphor.—Dry camphor (1 mol.) was dissolved in dry ether containing sodium beads (1 mol.) and after cooling

with ice, dimethylaminobenzaldehyde ($\frac{2}{3}$ mol.) was added when a vigorous reaction set in. The reaction mixture was kept below 5° for 2-3 hours and then refluxed for 20-30 minutes. The reddish brown pasty mass was extracted with ice-cold water and the ethereal layer on evaporation left behind a red viscous oil, which deposited reddish yellow crystals on long standing. These crystals were purified by dissolving in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitating with a solution of dilute sodium hydroxide. It crystallised from 90% alcohol in bright yellow glistening leaflets, m.p. $141-41.5^{\circ}$. (Found : N, 5.14. $C_{19}H_{25}ON$ requires N, 4.95 per cent). In the above experiment sodium can be replaced by sodium amalgam with advantage ; the reaction takes longer time for completion but gives a purer product.

Condensation Products of Camphoric Anhydride with Dialkylaminoanilines.—The method of preparation is described in previous papers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1966 ; 1927, 1994).

p-Methylethylaminocamphoranilic Acid.—Temperature $130-140^{\circ}$, duration of heating 4 hours. It crystallised from dilute alcohol as prisms, m.p. $179-80^{\circ}$. (Found : N, 8.49. $C_{19}H_{28}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.43 per cent).

p-Diethylaminocamphoranilic Acid.—Condensation temperature was $125-130^{\circ}$. It was purified by repeated dissolution in dilute acetic acid and precipitation with dilute ammonium hydroxide. It was obtained as prisms, m.p. $170.5-171^{\circ}$. (Found : N, 7.90. $C_{20}H_{30}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.09 per cent).

p-Dipropylaminocamphoranilic Acid.—Temperature, $130-135^{\circ}$, duration of heating 3-4 hours. A micro-crystalline compound with a yellowish tinge was obtained, m.p. 180.5° . (Found : N, 7.37. $C_{22}H_{34}O_3N_2$ requires N, 7.4 per cent).

p-Dibutylaminocamphoranilic Acid.—Temperature, $130-140^{\circ}$, duration of heating 3-4 hours. It was obtained as a crystalline powder with a greyish tinge, m.p. 126° after darkening at $112-113^{\circ}$. (Found : N, 6.87. $C_{24}H_{38}O_3N_2$ requires N, 6.96 per cent).

o-Diethylaminocamphoranilic Acid.—Temperature of condensation was $140-150^{\circ}$. It was obtained as a crystalline powder, shrinking at 147° and melting at $151-53^{\circ}$. (Found : N, 8.25. $C_{20}H_{30}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.09 per cent).

Condensation of d-Oxymethylenecamphor with p-Aminodialkylanilines.—*d-Oxymethylenecamphor* was prepared by the method of Claisen, Bishop and Sinclair (*Annalen*, 1894, 281, 331).

p-Dimethylaminoanilinomethylenecamphor.—A mixture of molecular quantities of *d-oxymethylenecamphor* and *p-aminodimethylaniline*, dissolved in the minimum quantities of pure methyl alcohol and dilute acetic

acid respectively, was gently warmed on the water-bath for about 5 minutes. On scratching for a few seconds, the condensation product settled out in a granular form and was crystallised from acetone (charcoal) in prismatic needles, m.p. 173-73.5° after darkening at 169°. It is readily soluble in acetone and methylethyl ketone, less so in methyl and ethyl alcohol and only sparingly soluble in benzene, and extremely soluble in chloroform and the solution changed in colour from light yellow to light green and ultimately to brown. But these changes were so instantaneous that it was not possible to take the reading in this solvent. It dyes wool yellow. (Found: N, 9.4. $C_{19}H_{26}ON_2$ requires N, 9.39 per cent).

p-Methylethylaminoanilinomethylenecamphor was prepared as in the foregoing experiment by condensing equimolecular proportions of *p*-aminomethylethylaniline and oxymethylenecamphor. It separated from 60-70% alcohol (charcoal) as a crystalline powder, m.p. 132-32.5° after changing colour at 123° and darkening at 126.5-128°. It is insoluble in water, but it readily dissolves in acetone or methylethyl ketone and is fairly soluble in methyl or ethyl alcohol and very readily in chloroform, the changes in colour being as usual. It dyes wool yellow. (Found: N, 9.12. $C_{20}H_{28}ON_2$ requires N, 8.97 per cent.).

p-Diethylaminoanilinomethylenecamphor was prepared by condensing *p*-dimethylaminoaniline and oxymethylenecamphor as usual. It crystallised from alcohol in prismatic needles, m.p. 134.5-35°. It is insoluble in water, but it dissolves readily in acetone or methyl ethyl ketone and is less soluble in methyl or ethyl alcohol. Its solubility in chloroform is appreciable and the solution undergoes sudden changes in colour and hence failure in taking any reading. The substance in alcoholic solution dyes wool yellow. (Found: N, 8.8. $C_{21}H_{30}ON_2$ requires N, 8.59 per cent).

p-Dipropylaminoanilinomethylenecamphor.—*p*-Aminodipropylaniline was obtained by preparing the nitroso derivative of dipropylaniline and then reducing the product with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid. The condensation was effected as in previous cases. The impure product obtained was crystallised twice from 70% alcohol in beautiful yellow crystalline powder, m.p. 136.5-137° after darkening at 128-29°. The filtrate on dilution gave a very good yield of the substance. It is soluble in the ordinary organic solvents, sparingly in benzene and insoluble in water. Quick changes in chloroform solution are observed. It dyes wool yellow. (Found: N, 8.06. $C_{23}H_{34}ON_2$ requires N, 7.9 per cent).

Condensation between *d*-oxymethylenecamphor and *p*-aminodiamylaniline under similar conditions gave a viscous mass which could not be crystallised.

m-Dimethylaminoanilinomethylenecamphor.—The mixture of *m*-dimethylaminoaniline and oxymethylenecamphor on prolonged warming and scratching yielded a microcrystalline solid which was crystallised twice from alcohol. It crumbles and becomes slightly yellowish at 158° and finally melts at 159·5-160°. It is soluble in the usual organic solvents but insoluble in water. Unlike *para*-compounds it exhibits no colour changes in chloroform and, therefore, the reading could very easily be taken. It has no dyeing properties. (Found: N, 9·2. C₁₉H₂₆ON₂ requires N, 9·39 per cent).

Condensation between *d*-oxymethylenecamphor and *o*-aminomethylaniline gave an oily product which could not be crystallised.

The rotatory powers were determined by dissolving a known weight of the substance in a known volume of the solvent. The following results without any mutarotation, were obtained. The readings within brackets were taken after the addition of hydrochloric acid.

p-Dimethylaminobenzylidenecamphor.

Solvent.	Conc. g./25 c.c.	α_D .	$[\alpha]_D$.	Solvent.	Conc. g./25 c.c.	α_D .	$[\alpha]_D$.
MeOH	0·0926	2·61	704·64	C ₆ H ₆	0·0903	2·22	614·60
		(1·27)	(342·87)				
(on addition of methyl iodide)	0·0978	2·43	621·17	C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₃	0·0852	2·04	598·59
EtOH	0·2000	5·85	731·25	C ₆ H ₅ Cl	0·1101	2·95	669·85
Me ₂ CO	0·1054	2·73	647·53	C ₆ H ₅ Br	0·1146	3·19	695·89
MeEtCO	0·0902	2·49	690·13	C ₆ H ₅ I	0·1578	3·48	551·33
CHCl ₃	0·0879	2·42	688·28	C ₆ H ₅ NO ₂	0·1165	3·24	695·28

p-Methylethylamino-camphoranilic acid.

MeOH	0·2638	0·64	60·65
		(0·66)	(62·54)
EtOH	0·2880	0·63	54·60
		(0·67)	(58·16)
Me ₂ CO	0·2093	0·40	47·78
MeEtCO	0·2048	0·41	50·05

p-Diethylamino-camphoranilic acid.

MeOH	0·2507	0·84	83·76
		(0·92)	(91·74)
EtOH	0·2175	0·68	78·16
		(0·75)	(86·21)
MeEtCO	0·2050	0·73	89·02
Me ₂ CO	0·2100	0·72	85·71
CHCl ₃	0·2000	0·65	81·25

p-Dipropylaminocamphoranilic acid.

Solvent	Conc. g./25 c.c.	α_D .	$[\alpha]_D$.
MeOH	0.1293	0.23	44.50
EtOH	0.1348	0.28	51.90
Me ₂ CO	0.1308	0.23	43.90

*p-Dibutylaminocamphoranilic acid.**o-Dimethylaminocamphoranilic acid.*

Solvent.	Conc. g/25 c.c	α_D .	$[\alpha]_D$.	Conc. g /25 c.c.	α_D .	$[\alpha]_D$.
MeOH	0.1670	0.37	55.40	0.2000	0	0
	"	(0.43)	(64.40)	0.3000	0	0
EtOH	0.1718	0.50	72.70	0.2006	-0.08	-9.97
Me ₂ CO	0.1705	0.41	60.00			
(Acid equiv. added in MeOH)				0.2000	0.44	55.00
(Acid equiv. added in EtOH)				0.2000	0.41	51.13

*o-Diethylaminocamphoranilic acid.**p-Dimethylaminoanilinomethylene-camphor.*

MeOH	0.2506	0.05	5.00	0.0552	0.75	339.67
		(0.39)	(38.90)		(0.54)	(244.56)
EtOH	0.2500	0.02	2.00	0.0500	0.61	305.00
		(0.20)	(20.00)			
Me ₂ CO	0.2628	-0.13	-12.30	0.0500	0.68	340.00
		(0.08)	(7.60)			
MeEtCO	0.2441	-0.12	-12.29	0.0550	0.79	359.90

*p-Methylethylaminoanilinomethylene-camphor.**p-Diethylaminoanilinomethylene-camphor.*

MeOH	0.0593	0.79	333.5	0.0576	0.70	303.82
		(0.57)	(240.30)		(0.51)	(221.35)
EtOH	0.0500	0.66	330.00	0.0516	0.69	315.93
Me ₂ CO	0.0500	0.66	330.00	0.0500	0.71	375.00
MeEtCO	0.0550	0.745	338.63	0.0601	0.88	366.06

<i>p</i> -Dipropylaminoanilinomethylene- camphor.				<i>m</i> -Dimethylaminoanilinomethylene- camphor.		
Solvent.	Conc. g./25 c.c.	α_D .	$[\alpha]_D$.	Conc. g./25 c.c.	α_D .	$[\alpha]_D$.
MeOH	0'0498	0'65	326'30	0'0551	0'71	322'14
		(0'58)	(291'16)	0'0522	0'71	340'38
EtOH	0'0528	0'71	336'17	0'0613	0'84	342'57
Me ₂ CO	0'0500	0'63	315'00		(0'92)	(375'20)
MeEtCO	0'0497	0'76	331'99	0'0677	0'83	302'31
					(0'91)	1336'06
CHCl ₃				0'0754	0'85	281'83

The readings were taken in dark room, the temperature varying from 19-22°.

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